

interstore

D6.5 – Final Communication and Dissemination Plan

Work Package 6 – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

Task 6.1 – Communication and Dissemination

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

WP	Work Package
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
EU	European Union
LFE	Linux Foundation Energy
HESS	Hybrid Energy Storage System
EV	Electric vehicle
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
US	United States

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The deliverable 6.5 “Final Communication and Dissemination Plan” provides a comprehensive overview of the communication and dissemination activities initially planned by InterSTORE, it updates them and presents the actions aimed at ensuring the long-term visibility of the project in terms of dissemination.

The first chapter presents the main goals and objectives of the communication and dissemination strategy followed throughout the project and the main stakeholder groups targeted in this. The second one presents the communication activities carried out in InterSTORE and how they have supported the efforts for dissemination and their role beyond the life of the project. The third chapter explains the internal procedures for the carrying out of these activities and the fourth one presents the performance assessment process and the different responsibilities taken on by partners within Work Package 6.

It is important to note that the aim of this deliverable is not to provide a detailed report on the results of the communication and dissemination activities, as this will be done in the final technical report, but to have an overview of the activities, update any actions taken and state how they will be relevant after the closure of InterSTORE.

1 Goals, Objectives and Stakeholders

1.1 Communication, and dissemination long-term goals and objectives

Work Package 6 aimed at increasing the visibility of the InterSTORE activities and results and its impacts through communication, dissemination and exploitation activities that have been going on since the beginning of the project. This work focused on increasing the ecosystem's size, scope and actions to amplify the impact of the project in socio-economic and scientific terms and push for raising public awareness and stakeholders' engagement.

The main goals of the Communication and Dissemination activities of InterSTORE were:

- Maximising the dissemination of project's results to the stakeholders, industry, suppliers and authorities to fasten the deployment of research findings.
- Stimulate the dissemination of the results through presentations during webinars, conferences and scientific publications.
- Pushing for the transferral of technology through the acceleration of the dissemination of the project activities and results to the relevant stakeholders, aiming to promote their exploitation and the adoption of common standards.
- Engaging in communication and dissemination activities with similar projects and initiatives to develop synergies and collaborations between other EU-funded actions
- Acquiring proper knowledge management, including appropriate managing of the IPR

1.2 Communication and dissemination strategy

The communication, dissemination and exploitation activities are part of WP6, led by EASE with all the partners as contributors. The methodology followed to develop the First Communication and Dissemination Plan and the Final Plan considers which inputs are worth to be disseminated, to which target groups and through which channels. For this final communication and dissemination plan the following priorities have been considered:

- Identify the targeted groups that have benefitted from the communication and dissemination efforts carried out by InterSTORE and thus are the recipients of the project,
- Define clear messages that accurately address the needs of each targeted audience, as they have been kept informed about the project developments.
- Analyse the dissemination and communication activities which are better tailored to transmit the messages with InterSTORE results with a business-oriented and societal intention.
- Contributions made to the working groups that could lead to policy recommendations.

The strategy that was elaborated focuses on empowering stakeholders and fostering community engagement through InterSTORE initiatives, creating opportunities for them to share their experiences and insights gained from the participation in the project. Moreover, community engagement played a key role in this strategy in demo sites, as it can create a collaborative approach leading to a sense of inclusivity and strengthening community bonds. This generated a more sustainable and effective implementation of the InterSTORE solutions.

The project consortium gave priority to places and channels where targeted audiences already gathered online and in person to obtain more exposure.

Furthermore, through the Triple layered business model canvas developed by InterSTORE, the societal, economic and environmental impacts of the project are better analysed and provided input to disseminate more efficiently the results. The Communication and Dissemination Plan has equipped this project for a rolling delivery flow of relevant news and content in multiple communication channels, mixing textual and visual content, maximising the impact of InterSTORE.

1.3 Stakeholder groups and management

To ensure the efficiency and publicity of the activities developed and the achievement of the goals, the project activities involving communication and dissemination were addressed to specific groups, specified in the First Communication and Dissemination Plan (D6.2) and identified by partners at the proposal stage. This was key in order to select the appropriate communication channels and tools to be used with each of them to achieve better results in the dissemination efforts of the project's message and outcomes.

The main objective for InterSTORE was to develop an innovative software that enables the integration of decentralised energy storage solutions to the power grids, offering flexible services by connecting multiple energy market participants and aggregating their supply and demand functions. Therefore, this project aims to deliver benefits for several stakeholders, providing socio-economical and technical developments, such as reduction of balancing costs. The entire value chain, from prosumers to energy trader, standardisation bodies and business and academic research units are involved in the project providing and profiting from the flexibility developed and the common communication standard developed.

Therefore, all the stakeholders have been reached through specific tools and channels tailored to their needs, selected to ensure their involvement and engagement, as well as a deep understanding of the project's work and results obtained.

Out of these stakeholders, a key one is the open-source community and Linux Foundation Energy, as it will be crucial for the sustainability of the solutions adopted and developed by the project. The open IP license used by InterSTORE has been the same as the one usually employed by the LFE (APACHE) and the results have been presented to the Foundation since the start of the project in their annual summits. This organisation will also continue to work on the outcomes of the project through a new project, CUPID (Controllable Unit Protocol for Interoperable Devices). Partners strongly believe in the value of the software developed and this will support the long-term sustainability to move to real application and concrete exploitation. The participation to the LFE is not limited to members but open to all the energy community.

The table below, which was already presented in D6.2 (First Communication and Dissemination Plan) presents the stakeholder groups (targeted audiences), the communication channels used and the goals achieved. Moreover, under task 6.3 Growing and managing the stakeholders, three meetings have been held, where these stakeholder groups have learned more about the work that has been carried out by InterSTORE and the results that were being achieved throughout the project. This will be further developed in section 2.11 of this deliverable.

Table 1. Targeted audiences, communication channels and goals

Target audience	Communication channels/tools	Goals
Pilot owners and HESS asset owners, energy suppliers and system operators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Posters -Leaflets -Newsletters -Social media -Website -Workshops/webinar -Conferences and events -Final event -Videos 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Raise sector's interest -Increase know-how -Raise awareness -Dissemination of project results
EV users, energy community, consumers and general public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Posters -Leaflets -Newsletters -Social media -Website -Webinars -Conferences and events -Final event -Videos 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Collect their feedback -Raise awareness of the technology development and innovation -Raise awareness of the society's role in energy.
European Commission and other initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Poster -Leaflet -Newsletter -Social media -Website -Webinars -Conferences and events -Final event -White Paper -Videos 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Mobilise the sector's interest -Foster cooperation -Raise awareness -Disseminate project's outcomes

Scientific Community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Posters -Leaflets -Newsletters -Social media -Website -Workshops and webinars -Conferences and events -Scientific publications -Final event 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Improve knowledge and know-how. -Raise awareness. -Create synergies. -Disseminate project results
Policymakers and public bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Events and conferences -White Paper -Final event 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Influence policy priorities -Use of project results for future policymaking
Inverter manufacturer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -IAB engagement -Dedicated workshop and training course on the tool developed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Enlarge InterSTORE IAB, ensuring that the tools and use-cases are market-driven -Increase the number of EU inverters manufacturers 2030.5 certified
Open-source community and Linux Foundation Energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Webinars and conferences -GitHub repository 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Ensure the long-term sustainability and updates of the tool development. -Continuity of InterSTORE through the CUPID project

2 Communication and Dissemination Tools and Resources

2.1 Visual identity

Since the submission of D6.2 there have not been any changes to the InterSTORE's visual identity. It was established in March 2023 and already reported in D6.1, Report the Project Identity and Website. It has played a key role throughout the duration of the whole project as it helped identify the project and it defined its brand identity. The visual identity included the logo, colour palette, typography and secondary identity elements. Its design, developed by an external provider, created a cohesive and professional appearance that helped stakeholders, partners and the general public to identify and engage with InterSTORE.

Figure 1 shows the InterSTORE logo. It contains the project acronym, which simplifies the reading of the full project name, and three elements that represent its complexity – the three cubes. The colour palette, varying from dark purple to turquoise, are usually associated with new technologies and innovation. Further information on this logo and the visual identity can be found on D6.1 Report on project identity and website.

Figure 1. InterSTORE logo

2.1.1 List of communication and dissemination materials

The visual identity and the logo have been used in the following materials (non-exhaustive list):

- Project website
- Social media
- Document templates, used in documents developed in the context of the project and especially those submitted to the European Commission such as deliverables
- Dissemination materials, including the roll-up, posters and leaflets
- Any in-person or online event organised by InterSTORE

The document templates support the project's efforts to maintain a clear and recognisable visual identity and help the public easily recognise the project. Following the colour scheme and fonts agreed, EASE prepared the following document templates.

- Deliverable template (Word)
- Text template (Word)
- Minutes of the meeting template (Word)
- Letterhead template (Word)
- Presentation template (PowerPoint)

TITLE

REVISION INDEX

Date	Version	Author	Comment
DD-MM-YY	1.0		The first draft
	2.0		Updated version
	FINAL		Final and submitted version

Figure 2. InterSTORE text template

Figure 3. InterSTORE PowerPoint template

2.2 Use of the EU flag and Disclaimer

Complying with Article 17.2 in the Grant Agreement, the EU support and funding has been acknowledged, by displaying the European flag (emblem) and the funding statement translated into local languages if appropriate in every communication and dissemination material developed. Moreover, this logo has had prominence if displayed with other ones. This has

been done by the beneficiaries in all communication activities related to InterSTORE, such as conferences, seminars or information materials including leaflets and roll-up. The InterSTORE consortium has been committed to respect and comply with this requirement and to maximise the efforts to give visibility to the EU support.

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Figure 4. European flag and funding statement

2.3 Project website

The InterSTORE website is one of the most important resources for the dissemination of the project results. It was developed to enhance the visibility of the project and the easy access to the resources for anyone from everywhere. Launched in April 2023, it follows the project's visual identity presented in the previous lines, serving as a reference to anyone interested in learning more about the project results and activities. Further, it is an additional channel to attract new stakeholders who might be interested in the tools developed by the project and in building partnerships with the consortium partners. EASE has been in charge of the design and maintenance of the website. This includes (non-exhaustive list):

- Update the project progress
- Add relevant news or events
- Add publications and public deliverables
- Include any other input considered relevant by the consortium to be displayed on the website
- Update information about the living labs

For these updates, EASE has heavily relied on the inputs provided by the project partners to ensure the appropriate content was being displayed online. Since the launch of the project, EASE has published 31 articles and pieces of news in the website which have served as input for the bi-annual newsletters.

It was made with the WordPress platform, allowing for adaptable and compatible content for visitors regardless of the device used (PC, mobile phone, tablet, etc). It has served to communicate the overview of the project, provide information about its objectives and relevant news, events and publications made by the project partners. The main purpose of the website has been to present and display relevant information about the project development and disseminate its results.

Figure 5. InterSTORE website homepage

The InterSTORE website results have been regularly analysed with Google Analytics. Since the start of 2025, 3.3k people has visited and engaged with the InterSTORE website (figure 6) with a peak around June which coincides with the 6th General Assembly held in Porto, Portugal. Most of these visitors come from outside the European Union (figure 7). Further analytics and results from the website will be provided in the final Technical Report.

Figure 6. Website visitors (2025)

Figure 7. Website visitors by country

2.3.1 Website domain

The website domain is <https://interstore-project.eu/> and it has been created on the WordPress platform, which provides user-friendly options for an accessible interface worldwide.

The website will remain alive until December 2030 following the Grant Agreement requirements, as it will serve as a reference for anyone wishing to consult anything related to the InterSTORE project and its results and activities. It will also serve as a central point to connect to all the repositories where project resources can be found, such as GitHub, Hub Docker or Zenodo.

2.4 Social media

Throughout its duration, InterSTORE has used LinkedIn and X (previously Twitter) as social media channels, which have complemented the role of the project website to increase the visibility, promote the project activities and maximise the dissemination of the results achieved. The public has been able to learn about the project's findings through the use of these social media channels. It has supported the work to reach the targeted audiences presented in the previous section and to spread information about the most recent news, activities, events and initiatives.

Both LinkedIn and X have been managed by EASE since their creation, creating relevant content with inputs received by the consortium and connecting with the audience. These communication tools provided a unique opportunity to build strong relationships with multiple groups and stakeholders, as it allowed them to provide their own feedback and connect with the partners directly through comments or chats.

2.4.1 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is a social media page mainly aimed at professional networking and it's related to business and professional activities. In the framework of this project, it has been used to communicate project updates and results with a formal language, as it is the aim of this social network and most of the followers of the InterSTORE page are professionals of great value that can provide very interesting insights and are interested in the connections that can be built through the project and allow to reach a wider audience. The InterSTORE LinkedIn profile is <https://www.linkedin.com/company/interstoreproject/>

Figure 8. Example of InterSTORE LinkedIn post

2.4.2 X (formerly Twitter)

X provides an online space to communicate in short messages (280 characters). It is mainly used for instant messaging and for communicating live events, although its use has decreased generally in the past few years and its relevance is lower than when the project started in 2023. The language and tone used in this social media channel has been less formal than in LinkedIn, as it is meant to communicate news and events to a more general audience and less connected to the topics covered in InterSTORE. As the messages shared in this channel are shorter, it is more suitable for covering live events or sharing news. The InterSTORE X profile is https://x.com/InterSTORE_eu

Figure 9. Example of InterSTORE X post

2.4.3 Social media analytics

Figure 10 shows the number of views that an InterSTORE post has on X. As mentioned in previous lines, this social media network has lost relevance since the beginning of the project.

Figure 10. X post dashboard with views

With LinkedIn analytics the InterSTORE performance can be studied. As it can be seen in the figure 11 below, there have been some peaks in the impressions of the InterSTORE LinkedIn page, coinciding with the promotion of the registrations for the final event and the actual final event in November 2025.

Figure 11. Impressions of InterSTORE LinkedIn posts

After these three years of active social media channels, it can be seen that LinkedIn performs better in terms of engaging with a wider audience. This could be related to the loss of relevance of X as a platform to stay up to date on scientific and technical topics. LinkedIn is a stronger channel to disseminate project results.

Table 2. Number of followers in each of the InterSTORE social media pages

Social media channel	Number of followers
LinkedIn	495
X	27

2.5 Newsletter

EASE has been in charge of sending out the bi-annual newsletters through the Mailchimp platform. Users were encouraged to subscribe to the newsletter through social media. Since the start of the project, five newsletters have been sent out and the last issue will be distributed before the end of M36 (December 2025). The final newsletter will include information about the project results achieved, the final event that has already taken place and the life of InterSTORE after its closure.

Every issue has had the same format and goal, including providing project updates, leading readers to the InterSTORE webpage to read the full articles presented in the email. They also offer updates on the most relevant events taking place. Table 3 presents the newsletters that have been sent out in the context of this project.

The Secretariat of EASE is run by CLERENS NV/SA, which is the data controller, responsible for processing personal data in accordance with GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation). More details regarding the Privacy Policy and Cookie Policy are available in <https://clerens.eu/privacy-cookie-policy/>.

Table 3. Newsletters sent out under InterSTORE

Date	Title	Opens and clicks
14 August 2023	InterSTORE Newsletter August 2023	46.7% and 13.3%
31 January 2024	InterSTORE Newsletter January 2024	22.7% and 22.7%
16 September 2024	InterSTORE Newsletter September 2024	67.9% and 32.1%
30 January 2025	InterSTORE Newsletter January 2025	56.5% and 10.9%
3 September 2025	InterSTORE Newsletter September 2025	46.9% and 8.8%

2.6 Promotional materials

As stated in the Grant Agreement, InterSTORE promotional materials included:

- A leaflet
- A roll-up
- 5 posters (a general one and one for each pilot – Spanish, German, Italian and Austrian)

The use of leaflets was meant to reach a general and non-specialist audience and relevant stakeholders with dissemination purposes. It was also distributed among partners so they could also have the opportunity to disseminate it in their own channels, networks and public events. The roll-up was aimed at being showcases at wide-scale events, such as Enlit 2024 or the InterSTORE final event. They have been designed respecting the visual identity of the project, as it can be seen in Fig. 12 (leaflet), Fig. 13 (roll-up) and Fig. 14 (general poster). Leaflets have been printed out in sufficient quantity and some examples have been archived in the EASE offices, as well as the roll-up, for future references.

Figure 12. InterSTORE leaflet

interstore

Interoperable open-source Tools to Enable hybridisation, utilisation, and monetisation of storage flexibility

DEPLOYED TECHNOLOGIES

- Consumers technologies
- Grid Technologies
- Large-scale storage
- Distributed storage

EMS DEPLOYED

- Residential power management system
- Home energy management system
- Flexibility management platform
- Generation technologies

STAY TUNED!
FOLLOW THE LATEST NEWS OF THE PROJECT!

Website | LinkedIn | Twitter

capWatt | CyberGrid | E.ON | E.ON | enel x | ...

MESS | INESC TEC | JÜLICH | ... | sunesic | VDE

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Figure 13. InterSTORE roll-up

interstore

InterSTORE is an EU-funded project that aims to deliver a set of interoperable Open-Source tools to integrate Distributed Energy Storage (DES) and Distributed Energy Resources (DER), to enable the hybridization, utilisation and monetisation of storage flexibility, within a real-life environment.

CONTEXT

The InterSTORE solution is widely demonstrated in its several perspectives by 4 Pilots to incorporate the hybridization solutions within homes, buildings, EV communities.

DEPLOYED TECHNOLOGIES

- Consumers technologies
- Grid Technologies
- Large-scale storage
- Distributed storage

EMS DEPLOYED

- Residential power management system
- Home energy management system
- Flexibility management platform
- Generation technologies

12 PARTNERS

7 COUNTRIES

36 MONTHS

4.3 MILLION BUDGET

capWatt | CyberGrid | E.ON | E.ON | enel x | ...

JÜLICH | ... | sunesic | VDE

STAY UP-TO-DATE WITH INTERSTORE'S LATEST DEVELOPMENTS!

Website | LinkedIn | Twitter

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Figure 14. InterSTORE general poster

2.7 Scientific materials

InterSTORE technical partners have submitted and published scientific articles in scientific journals and conferences aiming at disseminating project outcomes. All of them have been released in Gold and Green Open Access and have been peer reviewed. They are available either in the publisher's website or in the ZENODO <https://zenodo.org/> repository. Since the beginning of the project, twenty-eight articles, deliverables and presentations on different topics related to energy storage and interoperability have been made available in ZENODO under InterSTORE, achieving up to eighteen downloads in some of them. Table 4 presents the five scientific articles releases under open access in ZENODO

Project results have also been disseminated on GitHub <https://github.com/> and Hub Docker <https://hub.docker.com/>, where users can download the tools developed by InterSTORE, available in Open Access.

Table 4. Scientific materials published under InterSTORE available in open access in ZENODO

Date	Title	Partner	Journal
17 June 2024	Hybrid Energy Storage System Dispatch Optimization for Cost and Environmental Impact Analysis	INESC TEC	Energies
30 June 2024	Hybrid Energy Storage System sizing model based on load recurring pattern identification	INESC TEC	Journal of Energy Storage
2 April 2025	Controller Hardware-in-The-Loop Testing of a Multitimescale Control Architecture for Multienergy Systems	FZJ	IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Industrial Electronics
22 August 2025	Gaussian Process Supported Stochastic MPC for Distribution Grids	FZJ	IEEE Open Journal of Control Systems
25 November 2025	Adaptive Interoperable Management of Hybrid Energy Storage Systems for Grid-Forming Services	HESSTEC	IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications

2.8 Project videos

Two videos have been developed in the scope of InterSTORE. The first video, already published, is an animation which presents InterSTORE, its context, vision and objectives. It was made available on the project's YouTube channel on 11 September 2024 and elaborated by an external provider. It accurately presents what InterSTORE aimed to achieve in its 3-year duration, and it was widely promoted in the social media channels available and also by project partners.

The second video was recorded during the final event, which took place in Brussels in November 2025. During the event, some project partners were interviewed to share their experience and role in InterSTORE, what was achieved and why the outcomes of InterSTORE are relevant to the energy storage and interoperability community. It was later edited by an external provider and made available on the project's YouTube channel. It can also be found

on the website and it was disseminated on the social media channels available and by partners in their own networks.

2.9 Media

The project consortium has used press releases and news to disseminate the project activities and outcomes, and have been promoted in different channels such as newsletters, website and social media. All press materials related to the project such as the initial press release, are available on the website. Moreover, when partners have taken part in external events to raise the project's visibility, communication materials have been shared with the organisers to ensure the proper promotion in different networks.

2.10 Events

Since the beginning of the project, InterSTORE partners have worked together to organise events with other projects and initiatives, and have taken part in external ones to present the work done in the project and its outcomes. Moreover, EASE was in charge the InterSTORE final event, which took place in Brussels on 25 November 2025.

2.10.1 External events

InterSTORE project partners participated in multiple events since the start of the project with the aim of increasing the visibility of the project and disseminating its results. These external events have served as a platform to advocate for the solutions provided by the project outcomes in the field of interoperability and energy storage. Partners had the opportunity to engage with new stakeholders, raise awareness of the project and build a strong network to support the dissemination efforts, also relying on cooperation with similar projects and initiatives. Table 5 presents the events attended by partners.

Table 5. List of external events attended by partners under InterSTORE

Date	Event	Location	Partner involved
28-30 March 2025	BRIDGE Assembly	Brussels, Belgium	INESC TEC
20 April 2023	Hannover Messe	Hannover, Germany	VDE, FZJ
30 May-1 June 2023	Lisbon energy Summit	Lisbon, Portugal	CyberGrid, Sunesis
1-2 June 2023	Linux Foundation Energy Summit	Paris, France	CyberGrid, RWTH, Sunesis, EASE
26-30 June 2023	Embedded Open Source Summit	Prague, Czech Republic	CyberGrid, Sunesis
10-12 October 2023	Energy Storage Global Conference	Brussels, Belgium	EASE, ENEL X
28 November 2023	Enlit	Paris, France	EASE
17 January 2024	Interoperable hybrid distributed energy storage systems: the role of IEEE2030.5 and HESS dimensioning	Online	INESC TEC, Cyber-Grid

20 February 2024	E-world Essen 2024	Essen, Germany	RWTH, VDE
5 March 2023	OneNet Final event	Brussels, Belgium	RWTH, Engineering, INESC TEC
27-29 May 2025	IEEE ICSMARTGRID 2024	Setubal, Portugal	HESStec
9-10 October 2024	SEST 2024 Conference	Torino, Italy	INESC TEC
22-24 November 2024	Enlit	Milan, Italy	RWTH, EASE
26-27 November 2024	Battery Innovation Days 2024	Barcelona, Spain	CyberGrid
28-29 November 2024	RT24 - Real Time Simulation Conference	Edinburg, UK	FZJ
25-26 March 2025	BRIDGE General Assembly	Brussels, Belgium	RWTH, EASE, INESC TEC, Engineering
3 April 2025	Hannover Messe 2025	Hannover, Germany	VDE, CyberGrid
29 April 2024	All Electric Society	Berlin, Germany	VDE
7-9 May 2025	The Smarter E Europe	Munich, Germany	EASE, CyberGrid
29 June - 3 July 2025	IEEE POWERTECH 2025	Kiel, Germany	HESStec
10-12 June 2025	EUSEW 2025	Brussels, Belgium	FZJ, Engineering, INESC TEC, EASE
24-6 June 2025	ICCEP 2025	Villasimius, Italy	FZJ
10-11 September 2025	Linux Foundation Energy Summit Europe 2025	Aachen, Germany	RWTH, INESC TEC, Engineering
18-20 November 2025	Enlit Europe	Bilbao, Spain	CyberGrid

As the project is over, partners will still have opportunities to disseminate its outcomes and results in events where they are taking part in but not as representatives of InterSTORE. An example of this would be the energy fairs attended by VDE, where they will be able to still share leaflets and speak about the work done throughout the duration of the project. As a standardisation organisation, VDE will keep showing InterSTORE as an example of interoperability focused on energy.

2.10.2 Workshops, webinars and clustering activities

As mentioned in the grant agreement, EASE was responsible for organising workshops, webinars and clustering activities. During the duration of the project, EASE organised 6 webinars:

Table 6. InterSTORE organised webinars

Date	Title	Location
17 January 2023	Power and Energy Webinar	Online
12 July 2023	Cluster Meeting: InterSTORE, FLEXCHESS and PARMENIDES	Online
16 October 2024	Interoperable concept for the energy communities. Different perspectives from the InterSTORE-FLEXCHESS-PARMENIDES projects	Online
6 November 2024	Implementation of Data space and interoperability for flexibility services using DES. Different perspectives from the InterSTORE-FLEXCHESS-PARMENIDES projects	Online
26 May 2025	Advancing Interoperability and Innovation in Distributed Energy Systems	Online
11 February 2026	SunSpec Alliance Webinar	Online

After the project closure, partners will take part in a webinar organised by the SunSpec Alliance in February 2026, an organisation based in the US which has developed the IEEE 2030.5 standard, which has been used by our project. During this webinar, partners will present to the SunSpec Alliance audience how InterSTORE has used the IEEE 2030.5 standard in its testing activities. This will give the project access to a wider international and non-European audience of potential adopters.

2.10.3 Final event

The InterSTORE final event took place in Brussels on 25 November 2025. There were 59 registrations, with 28 online attendees and 31 in person. It is important to note that this event took place in the midst of a three-day national strike in Belgium, which heavily disrupted transportation and services in Brussels.

This was an opportunity for partners to present the results achieved during the three years of the project. The agenda including presentations about the work done under InterSTORE, the four pilots and how the project results will be kept alive through the CUPID project in the Linux Foundation Energy.

Moreover, there were two external speakers. Rolf Riemenschneider, Head of Sector at DG CONNECT in the European Commission, delivered a keynote speech on the role of open-source platforms in accelerating Europe's energy transition, which strongly aligned with the goals and vision of the project and represented the work that has been done during the past three years. The second external speaker was Erin Mahan, Vice President of Membership and Regulatory Affairs at the SunSpec Alliance, who presented the audience with the SunSpec IEEE2030.5 standard and its success stories, which was a very interesting insight for participants as this test standard has been used in InterSTORE.

This final event was an opportunity to host discussions to effectively present the project results and to provide a space for networking, fostering collaboration among partners and stakeholders and engaging with the external audience. This final event was organised by EASE as the Work Package 6 leader.

Figure 15. InterSTORE consortium at the final event

2.11 Stakeholder meetings

Under task 6.3 Growing and Managing the stakeholders' group, EASE, in collaboration with the rest of the consortium, has identified crucial stakeholders that have created an ecosystem that fed the project results and supported the goal of bridging the gaps with industry. EASE was strongly supported by INESC TEC contributing to the stakeholder group composition and document preparation, as well as ENEL X and Engineering.

Throughout the project, there have been three stakeholder group meetings. These meetings have served to get feedback from external parties who could also become potential adopters of the technologies developed by InterSTORE, as well as to announce project developments, such as InterSTORE's transition into the Linux Foundation for Energy as the CUPID project, ensuring the continuity of the tools beyond the project's funding horizon and invites wider community contributions. All consortium partners were involved in these meetings.

2.12 White Paper

In the beginning of 2025, InterSTORE published its White Paper, The Role of the IEEE 2030.5 Interoperability Standard in Distributed Energy Resources Integration, which explores the key findings within the framework of the InterSTORE project, highlighting the IEEE 2030.5 standard role, challenges and recommendations for widespread adoption. IEEE 2030.5 plays a key role in the transition to decentralised, digitalised and efficient energy systems and InterSTORE demonstrates the potential of the protocol to streamline its adoption. However, policy support, infrastructure investment and simplified certification remain critical to overcoming adoption challenges.

This White Paper was widely disseminated through the project's communication channels, including the website and social media. Information was also facilitated to the project partners to promote it through their own networks and channels. It was also aimed at policy-makers, including Members of the European Parliament and the European Commission.

THE ROLE OF THE IEEE 2030.5
INTEROPERABILITY STANDARD
IN DISTRIBUTED ENERGY RESOURCES
INTEGRATION

White Paper

Figure 16. InterSTORE White Paper

3 Internal coordination and procedures

EASE played a key role in coordinating the Communication and Dissemination activities of InterSTORE as the Work Package 6 leader. EASE has relied on the inputs provided by partners to create content and develop communication materials, adapting the material provided by them.

Consortium partners have been committed to deliver the content for the website and social media, as well as had the right to tag the InterSTORE project on social media and promote the materials through their own communication channels. External content was also published on InterSTORE communication channels if EASE decided so. If any project partner had an opportunity to speak with the media, all the materials required (leaflets, presentations, etc.) were provided by the relevant partner organisation.

Regarding the internal repository, it was initially hosted on Teams as a SharePoint, but it was then later taken on by RWTH Aachen University and now it can be found on the Sciebo platform. This has supported the efforts of maintaining transparency within the consortium and of improving the efficiency of the collaborative work. Additionally, there have been monthly WP6 meetings to monitor the activities of each task under the WP. The PowerPoint presentations used for these meetings remain available on the internal repository.

Following the Grant Agreement article 1.2.6 on open science implementation, scientific publications under InterSTORE have been released as Gold and Green Open Access peer-reviewed, as it is also stated on section 2.7 of this deliverable. The commitment towards the EC policy of openness, integrity and reproducibility is ensured through the open access to peer-reviewed publications related to the project results.

4 Performance assessment

To monitor the results of the Communication and Dissemination activities and stakeholder engagement, a set of Key Performance Indicators was identified and have served as a reference throughout the duration of the project. These results were presented every six months to all consortium partners during the General Assembly meetings.

4.1 Key Performance Indicators

Each communication channel provides its own monitoring tools. A detailed report of the results will be provided in the final technical report. The table 7 below presents the KPIs of all the communication activities.

Table 7. List of Key Performance Indicators

Tool	Indicator	Target	Result
Brochures	#brochures distributed	At least 200 per year	150
Posters	#poster produced	5 in total <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 general • 1 for pilot 	5 posters produced
E-Newsletter	#NL and # subscribers	2 per year 500 registered addresses	6 (two per year) 119 registered addresses
White Paper	#Industry, Standardization and Policy Makers reached	Top level standardized organization and at least 1 EU parliament and EU commissioner reached	Disseminated in the project's communication tools and channels
Social Networks	#followers on LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube	>3500; >9000; >1000	495 27 3
Workshops/Webinars	#workshop and #of participants	4 workshops (100 parts/average)	6 webinars 45
Participation in conferences/events	#of events attended	>8 per year	18
Videos	#video and average, #views	2 videos and >500 views/Video	5 videos, 339 views
Scientific Publications	#peer-reviewed papers/articles	>10 by the end of the project	5
Website	#unique visitors	>1000/yr	3400 visitors
Final meeting	#of participants	>300	30

4.2 Deliverables

Table 8 below presents the deliverables published within WP6 in InterSTORE.

Table 8. List of deliverables under WP6

Deliverable	Month due	Responsible partner	Status
D6.1 Report on project identity and website	M3	EASE	Submitted
D6.2 First Communication and Dissemination Plan	M6	EASE	Submitted
D6.3 First draft of the Exploitation Strategy, Plan and IPR report	M12	ENEL X	Submitted
D6.4 Final Exploitation Roadmap including Business Plan and IPR Report	M36	RWTH	Submitted
D6.5 Final Communication and Dissemination Plan	M36	EASE	Submitted

4.3 Partners responsibility

Table 9 below provides an overview of the EASE team involved in the Communication and Dissemination activities.

Table 9. Communications team

Organisation	Main Communication Responsible	Support
EASE	Sara Pernas Paredes	Stefani Krečar
		Fatima Ahmed

EASE remained responsible for Task 6.1 Communication and Dissemination, which includes the communication activities presented in chapter 2 of this deliverable. EASE also led Task 6.3 on growing and managing the stakeholder group with the aim of increasing the impact of the project and engage with more stakeholders supported by all partners, especially INESC TEC. Under this task there were regular meetings held to present and refine the project main developments, ensuring that the tools developed. Throughout the project, the costs of the communication tools and materials were allocated to EASE budget, including printed materials, website maintenance, video editing and logistical planning for these. Partners paid for events where they promoted the project and its outcomes with the budget allocated for such activities.

Task 6.2 on technology transfer to DES manufacturers was managed by VDE, in collaboration with Sunesis, CyberGrid, RWTH, INESC TEC and Engineering and their progress was reported

on the monthly WP6 meetings. Task 6.4 and 6.5, focused on exploitation activities, were led by EASE and RWTH. Their focus has been ensuring the long-term sustainability of the project outcomes, maximising the economic impact of the solution and the contribution to a more digitalised and decarbonised energy systems with open-source tools.

5 Conclusion

The deliverable 6.5 “Final Communication and Dissemination Plan” is a comprehensive overview of the work that has been done in terms of communication and dissemination efforts during the three years of InterSTORE and defines how the project will be kept alive in these terms, ensuring its visibility and impact beyond its duration. Examples of how it will be kept alive can be found throughout this document, such as in the leaflet distribution in energy fairs, webinars as the one planned with the SunSpec Alliance or the uptake of InterSTORE by the Linux Foundation for Energy through the CUPID project.

However, it is important to consider that the actual results of the communication efforts and activities will be reported in the final technical report. This document has served as an update of D6.2 “First Communication and Dissemination Plan”, reporting on any changes that have taken place and updating the activities that have taken place.

As InterSTORE ends, its work and results will be uptaken by the CUPID project, under the Linux Foundation Energy, aligning with its goals and mission of promoting open-source solutions for the energy transmission. This confirms the project commitment to provide long-term sustainable results beyond its lifespan and it has increased the visibility of InterSTORE in the open-source energy community. The CUPID project will ensure continuity of the tools beyond the project’s funding horizon and invites wider community contributions.

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